

*- Neutrosophic Crisp Set & *- Neutrosophic Crisp relations

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Abstract. Since the world is full of indeterminacy, the neutrosophics found their place into contemporary research. The purpose of this paper is to introduce a new type of neutrosophic crisp set as the *- neutrosophic crisp sets as a generalization to star intuitionistic set due to Indira et al.[4], and study some of

Keywords: Neutrosophic Crisp Set; Star Intuitionistic Sets; Neutrosophic Relations; Neutrosophic Data.

1 Introduction

The fundamental concepts of neutrosophic set, introduced by Smarandache in [31, 32, 33], and Salama et al. in [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30], provides a natural foundation for treating mathematically the neutrosophic phenomena which exist pervasively in our real world and for building new branches of neutrosophic mathematics. Neutrosophy has laid the foundation for a whole family of new mathematical theories generalizing both their classical and fuzzy counterparts [1, 2, 12, 22, 34] such as a neutrosophic set theory. In this paper we introduce a new type of neutrosophic crisp set as the *- neutrosophic crisp set, and study some of its properties. Finally we introduce and study the notion of *- neutrosophic relation and some of its properties. Possible applications to mathematical computer are touched upon.

2 Terminologies

We recollect some relevant basic preliminaries, and in particular, the work of Smarandache in [31, 32, 33], and Salama et al. in [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30]. Smarandache introduced the neutrosophic components T, I, F which represent the membership, indeterminacy, and non-membership values respectively, where $]0, 1[$ is nonstandard unit interval.

3 *- Neutrosophic Crisp Sets

We shall now consider some possible definitions for a new type of neutrosophic crisp set

Definition 3.1

its properties. Finally we introduce and study the notion of *- neutrosophic relation and some of its properties.

Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic crisp set (NCS for short) A is an object having the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$.

Then we define the *- neutrosophic set A^* as $A^* = \langle A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c, A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c \rangle$ where A_1, A_2 and A_3 are subsets of X such that

$M = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c$, $S = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c$ and $R = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c$.

A *- neutrosophic crisp set is an object having the form $A^* = \langle M, S, R \rangle$

Lemma 3.1

Let X be a non-empty fixed sample space. A neutrosophic crisp set (NCS for short) A is an object having the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$. Then

$A^* = \langle A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c, A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c \rangle$ is also a neutrosophic crisp set.

Proof

It's clear.

Corollary 3.1

Let X be a non-empty fixed set. Then ϕ_N^* and X_N^* are also neutrosophic crisp set.

Theorem 3.1

Let X be a non-empty fixed sample space, two neutrosophic crisp sets A, B are having the form

$A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$, $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, and two *- neutrosophic sets $A^* = \langle M_1, S_1, R_1 \rangle$, $B^* = \langle M_2, S_2, R_3 \rangle$ where

$M_1 = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c$, $S_1 = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c$,

$$R_1 = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c, M_2 = B_1 \cap (B_2 \cup B_3)^c, \\ S_2 = B_2 \cap (B_1 \cup B_3)^c, \text{ and}$$

$R_2 = B_3 \cap (B_1 \cup B_2)$, Then $A \subseteq B$ implies $A^* \subseteq B^*$.

Proof

Given $A \subseteq B$. Then it is easy to prove that $M_1 \subseteq M_2$, $S_1 \subseteq S_2, R_1 \supseteq R_2$ or $M_1 \subseteq M_2, S_1 \subseteq S_2, R_1 \supseteq R_2$ So $A^* \subseteq B^*$.

Remark 3.1

- 1) All types of ϕ_N^* and ϕ_N are conceded.
- 2) All types of X_N^* and X_N are conceded.
- 3) $A^* = B^*$ iff $A^* \subseteq B^*$ and $B^* \subseteq A^*$.

Definition 3.8

Let X be a non-empty set, and $A^* = \langle M, S, R \rangle$ be a *- neutrosophic crisp set on a NCS $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ where $M = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, S = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c, R = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c$, Then the complement of the set A^* (A^{*c} , for short) may be defined as three kinds of complements

(C₁) Type1: $A^{*c} = \langle M^c, S^c, R^c \rangle,$

(C₂) Type2: $A^{*c} = \langle R, S, M \rangle,$

(C₃) Type3: $A^{*c} = \langle R, S^c, M \rangle.$

Definition 2.3

Let X be a non-empty fixed set, two neutrosophic crisp sets A, B are having the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle, B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, and two *- neutrosophic crisp sets $A^* = \langle M_1, S_1, R_1 \rangle, B^* = \langle M_2, S_2, R_2 \rangle$ where $M_1 = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3)^c, S_1 = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3)^c, R_1 = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2)^c, M_2 = B_1 \cap (B_2 \cup B_3)^c, S_2 = B_2 \cap (B_1 \cup B_3)^c$, and

$R_2 = B_3 \cap (B_1 \cup B_2)^c$, Then

- 1) $A^* \cap B^*$ may be defined as two types:
 - i) Type1: $A^* \cap B^* = \langle M_1 \cap M_1, S_2 \cap S_2, R_3 \cup R_3 \rangle$ or
 - i. Type2: $A^* \cap B^* = \langle M_1 \cap M_1, S_2 \cup S_2, R_3 \cup R_3 \rangle$
- 4) $A^* \cup B^*$ may be defined as two types:
 - i) Type1: $A^* \cup B^* = \langle M_1 \cup M_1, S_2 \cap S_2, R_3 \cap R_3 \rangle$ or
 - ii) Type2: $A^* \cup B^* = \langle M_1 \cup M_1, S_2 \cup S_2, R_3 \cap R_3 \rangle.$

Lemma 3.1

Let A^*, B^* are *- neutrosophic crisp sets. Then $A^* - B^* = A^* \cap B^{*c}$
 It easy to show that L. H. S is also a *- neutrosophic crisp sets.

Example 3.2

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}$, $A = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \{f\} \rangle,$
 $B = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{d\}, \{e\} \rangle, C = \langle \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{e, f, a\} \rangle$
 $D = \langle \{a, b\}, \{e, c\}, \{f, d\} \rangle$ are NCS. Then
 $A^* = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \{f\} \rangle, B^* = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{d\}, \{e\} \rangle,$
 $C^* = \langle \{b\}, \{c, d\}, \{e, f\} \rangle,$

The complement may be equal as:

- 1) $A^{*c} = \langle \{e, f\}, \{a, b, c, d, f\}, \{a, b, c, d\} \rangle,$
 $A^{*c} = \langle \{\{f\}, \{e\}, \{a, b, c, d\}\}, A^{*c} = \langle \{\{f\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, \{a, b, c, d\}\},$
 $2) C^{*c} = \langle \{a, c, d, f\}, \{a, b, e, f\}, \{a, b, c, d\} \rangle,$
 $C^{*c} = \langle \{e, f\}, \{c, d\}, \{b\} \rangle, C^{*c} = \langle \{e, f\}, \{a, b, e, f\}, \{b\} \rangle.$
- 3) $A^* \cup B^*$ may be equals the following forms
 $A^* \cup B^* = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \phi \rangle,$
 $A^* \cup B^* = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \phi, \{f\} \rangle,$
- 4) $A^* \cap B^*$ may be equals the following forms
 $A^* \cap B^* = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{e, d\}, \{f, e\} \rangle,$
 $A^* \cap B^* = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \phi, \{f, e\} \rangle,$

Proposition 3.1

Let $\{A_j^* : j \in J\}$ be arbitrary family of *- neutrosophic crisp subsets on X , then

- 1) $\cap A_j^*$ may be defined two types as :
 - i) Type1: $\cap A_j^* = \langle \cap M_j, \cap S_j, \cup R_j \rangle,$ or
 - ii) Type2: $\cap A_j^* = \langle \cap M_j, \cup S_j, \cup R_j \rangle.$
- 2) $\cup A_j^*$ may be defined two types as :
 - i) Type1: $\cup A_j^* = \langle \cup M_j, \cap S_j, \cap R_j \rangle$ or
 - ii) Type2: $\cup A_j^* = \langle \cup M_j, \cup S_j, \cap R_j \rangle.$

Corollary 3.2

Let $\{A_i\}$ be a NCSs in X where $i \in J$, where J is an index set and $\{A_i^*\}$ are corresponding *- neutrosophic crisp subsets on X then

- a) $A_i^* \subseteq B^*$ for each $i \in J \Rightarrow \cup A_i^* \subseteq B^*.$
- b) $B^* \subseteq A_i^*$ for each $i \in J \Rightarrow B^* \subseteq \cup A_i^*.$
- c) $(\cup A_i^*)^c = \cap A_i^{*c}; (\cap A_i^*)^c = \cup A_i^{*c}.$

d) $A_i^* \subseteq B^* \Leftrightarrow B^{*c} \subseteq A^{*c}$.

e) $A^{*c^c} = A$,

f) $\phi_N^{*c} = X_N; X_N^{*c} = \phi_N^*$.

Now we shall define the image and preimage of *-neutrosophic crisp set.

Let X, Y be two non-empty fixed sets and $f: X \rightarrow Y$, be a function and $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$, $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ are neutrosophic crisp sets on X and Y respectively, $A^* = \langle M_1, S_1, R_1 \rangle$, $B^* = \langle M_2, S_2, R_2 \rangle$ be the *-neutrosophic crisp sets on X and Y respectively.

Definition 3.9

- (a) If B^* is a *-NCS in Y , then the preimage of B^* under f , denoted by $f^{-1}(B^*)$, is a *-NCS in X defined by $f^{-1}(B^*) = \langle f^{-1}(M_2), f^{-1}(S_2), f^{-1}(R_2) \rangle$
- (b) If A^* is a *-NCS in X , then the image of A^* under f , denoted by $f(A^*)$, is the *-NCS in Y defined by $f(A^*) = \langle f(M_1), f(S_1), f(R_1)^c \rangle$.

Here we introduce the properties of images and preimages some of which we shall frequently use in the following.

Corollary 3.2

Let $A^*, \{A_i^* : i \in J\}$, be a family of *-NCS in X , and $B^*, \{B_j^* : j \in K\}$ *-NCS in Y , and $f: X \rightarrow Y$ a function. Then

- (a) $A^*_1 \subseteq A^*_2 \Leftrightarrow f(A^*_1) \subseteq f(A^*_2)$,
 $B^*_1 \subseteq B^*_2 \Leftrightarrow f^{-1}(B^*_1) \subseteq f^{-1}(B^*_2)$,
- (b) $A^* \subseteq f^{-1}(f(A^*))$ and if f is injective, then $A^* = f^{-1}(f(A^*))$,
- (c) $f^{-1}(f(B^*)) \subseteq B^*$ and if f is surjective, then $f^{-1}(f(B^*)) = B^*$,
- (d) $f^{-1}(\cup B^*_i) = \cup f^{-1}(B^*_i)$, $f^{-1}(\cap B^*_i) = \cap f^{-1}(B^*_i)$,
- (e) $f(\cup A^*_ii) = \cup f(A^*_ii)$; $f(\cap A^*_ii) \subseteq \cap f(A^*_ii)$; and if f is injective, then $f(\cap A^*_ii) = \cap f(A^*_ii)$;
- (f) $f^{-1}(Y^*_N) = X^*_N$, $f^{-1}(\phi^*_N) = \phi^*_N$.
- (g) $f(\phi^*_N) = \phi^*_N$, $f(X^*_N) = Y^*_N$, if f is surjective.
- (h) If f is surjective, then $(f(A^*))^c \subseteq f(A^*)^c$. if furthermore f is injective, then have $(f(A^*))^c = f(A^*)^c$.
- (i) $(f^{-1}(B^*))^c = (f^{-1}(B^*))^c$.

Proof

Clear by definitions.

4 *- Neutrosophic Crisp Set Relations

Here we give the definition relation on *-neutrosophic crisp sets and study of its properties.

Let X, Y and Z be three ordinary nonempty sets

Definition 4.1

Let X be a non-empty fixed set, two neutrosophic crisp sets A, B are having the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$,

$B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, and two *-neutrosophic crisp

sets $A^* = \langle M_1, S_1, R_1 \rangle, B^* = \langle M_2, S_2, R_2 \rangle$ where

$M_1 = A_1 \cap (A_2 \cup A_3), S_1 = A_2 \cap (A_1 \cup A_3),$

$R_1 = A_3 \cap (A_1 \cup A_2),$

$M_2 = B_1 \cap (B_2 \cup B_3), S_2 = B_2 \cap (B_1 \cup B_3),$ and

$R_2 = B_3 \cap (B_1 \cup B_2)$, Then

- i) The product of two *-neutrosophic crisp sets A^* and B^* is a *-neutrosophic crisp set $A^* \times B^*$ given by $A^* \times B^* = \langle M_1 \times M_2, S_1 \times S_2, R_1 \times R_2 \rangle$ on $X \times Y$.
- ii) We will call a *-neutrosophic crisp relation $R^* \subseteq A^* \times B^*$ on the direct product $X \times Y$.

The collection of all *-neutrosophic crisp relations on $X \times Y$ is denoted as $SNCR(X \times Y)$

Definition 4.2

Let R^* be a *-neutrosophic crisp relation on $X \times Y$, then the inverse of R^* is denoted by R^{*-1} where $R^* \subseteq A^* \times B^*$ on $X \times Y$ then $R^{*-1} \subseteq B^* \times A^*$ on $Y \times X$.

Example 4.1

Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}$, $A = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \{f\} \rangle$,

$B = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{d\}, \{e\} \rangle$, are NCS.

Then $A^* = \langle \{a, b, c, d\}, \{e\}, \{f\} \rangle$, $B^* = \langle \{a, b, c\}, \{d\}, \{e\} \rangle$, then the product of two *-neutrosophic crisp sets given by

$A^* \times B^* = \langle \{(a, a), (a, b), (a, c), (b, a), (b, b), (b, c), (c, a), (c, b), (c, c)\}, \{(e, d)\}, \{(f, e)\} \rangle$ and

$B^* \times A^* = \langle \{(a, a), (a, b), (a, c), (a, d), (b, a), (b, b), (b, c), (b, d), (c, a), (c, b), (c, c), (c, d)\}, \{(d, e)\}, \{(e, f)\} \rangle$

, and $R_1^* = \langle \{(a, a)\}, \{(c, c)\}, \{(d, d)\} \rangle, R_1^* \subseteq A^* \times B^*$ on $X \times X$,

$R_2^* = \langle \{(a, b)\}, \{(c, c)\}, \{(d, d), (b, d)\} \rangle, R_2^* \subseteq B^* \times A^*$ on

$X \times X$, $R_1^{*-1} = \langle \{(a, a)\}, \{(c, c)\}, \{(d, d)\} \rangle \subseteq B^* \times A^*$ and

$R_2^{*-1} = \langle \{(b, a)\}, \{(c, c)\}, \{(d, d), (d, b)\} \rangle \subseteq B^* \times A^*$.

We can define the operations of *-neutrosophic crisp relations.

Definition 4.3

Let R^* and S^* be two *-neutrosophic crisp relations between X and Y for every $(x, y) \in X \times Y$ and NCSS A

and B in the form $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$, A^* on X ,
 $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, B^* on Y Then we can defined the following operations

- i) $R \subseteq S$ may be defined as two types
- a) Type1: $R^* \subseteq S^* \Leftrightarrow M_{1R} \subseteq M_{1S}, S_{1R} \subseteq S_{1S},$

$$R_{1R} \supseteq R_{1S}$$

- b) Type2:

$$R^* \subseteq S^* \Leftrightarrow M_{1R} \subseteq M_{1S}, S_{1R} \supseteq S_{1S}, R_{1R} \supseteq R_{1S}$$

- ii) $R^* \cup S^*$ may be defined as two types

- a) Type1:

$$R^* \cup S^* = \langle M_{1R} \cup M_{1S}, S_{1R} \cup S_{1S}, R_{1R} \cap R_{1S} \rangle,$$

- b) Type2:

$$R^* \cup S^* = \langle M_{1R} \cup M_{1S}, S_{1R} \cap S_{1S}, R_{1R} \cap R_{1S} \rangle.$$

- iii) $R^* \cap S^*$ may be defined as two types

- a) Type1:

$$R^* \cap S^* = \langle M_{1R} \cap M_{1S}, S_{1R} \cup S_{1S}, R_{1R} \cup R_{1S} \rangle,$$

- b) Type2:

$$R^* \cap S^* = \langle M_{1R} \cap M_{1S}, S_{1R} \cap S_{1S}, R_{1R} \cup R_{1S} \rangle.$$

Theorem 4.1

Let R^* , S^* and Q^* be three *- neutrosophic crisp relations between X and Y for every $(x, y) \in X \times Y$, then

- i) $R^* \subseteq S^* \Rightarrow R^{*-1} \subseteq S^{*-1}$.
- ii) $(R^* \cup S^*)^{-1} \Rightarrow R^{*-1} \cup S^{*-1}$.
- iii) $(R^* \cap S^*)^{-1} \Rightarrow R^{*-1} \cap S^{*-1}$.
- iv) $(R^{*-1})^{-1} = R^*$.
- v) $R^* \cap (S^* \cup Q^*) = (R^* \cap S^*) \cup (R^* \cap Q^*)$.
- vi) $R^* \cup (S^* \cap Q^*) = (R^* \cup S^*) \cap (R^* \cup Q^*)$.
- vii) If $S^* \subseteq R^*$, $Q^* \subseteq R^*$, then $S^* \cup Q^* \subseteq R^*$.

Proof

Clear

Definition 5.4

The *- neutrosophic crisp relation $I^* \in SNCR^*(X \times X)$, the *- neutrosophic crisp relation of identity may be defined as two types

- i) Type1: $I^* = \langle \{A^* \times A^*\}, \{A^* \times A^*\}, \phi^* \rangle$
- ii) Type2: $I^* = \langle \{A^* \times A^*\}, \phi^*, \phi^* \rangle$

Now we define two composite relations of *- neutrosophic crisp sets.

Definition 5.5

Let R^* be a *- neutrosophic crisp relation in $X \times Y$, and S^* be a neutrosophic crisp relation in $Y \times Z$. Then the

composition of R^* and S^* , $R^* \circ S^*$ be a *- neutrosophic crisp relation in $X \times Z$ as a definition may be defined as two types

- i) Type1:

$$R^* \circ S^* \leftrightarrow (R^* \circ S^*)(x, z) \\ = \cup \{ \langle \{ (M_1 \times M_2)_R \cap (M_1 \times M_2)_S \}, \\ \{ (S_1 \times S_2)_R \cap (S_1 \times S_2)_S \}, \{ (R_1 \times R_2)_R \cap (R_1 \times R_2)_S \} \rangle .$$

- ii) Type2:

$$R^* \circ S^* \leftrightarrow (R^* \circ S^*)(x, z) \\ = \cap \{ \langle \{ (M_1 \times M_2)_R \cup (M_1 \times M_2)_S \}, \\ \{ (S_1 \times S_2)_R \cup (S_1 \times S_2)_S \}, \{ (R_1 \times R_2)_R \cup (R_1 \times R_2)_S \} \rangle .$$

Theorem 4.2

Let R^* be a *- neutrosophic crisp relation in $X \times Y$, and S be a *- neutrosophic crisp relation in $Y \times Z$ then $(R^* \circ S^*)^{-1} = S^{*-1} \circ R^{*-1}$.

Proof

Let $R^* \subseteq A^* \times B^*$ on $X \times Y$ then $R^{*-1} \subseteq B \times A$,
 $S^* \subseteq B^* \times D^*$ on $Y \times Z$ then $S^{*-1} \subseteq D^* \times B^*$, from Definition 4.3 and similarly we can $I^{*(R^* \circ S^*)^{-1}}(x, z) = I^{*S^{*-1}}(x, z)$ and $I^{*R^{*-1}}(x, z)$ then $(R^* \circ S^*)^{-1} = S^{*-1} \circ R^{*-1}$.

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